

Supplement to American Heart Association Standards for Neuroprognostication in Comatose Survivors of Cardiac Arrest

Erik Ole Jørgensen

MD, retired lecturer and physician in chief, Copenhagen University Hospitals
Vingårds Alle 24, 2900 Hellerup
Tel: +45 2990 0781
e-mail: e.o.jorgensen@hotmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-003-1538-8565>

Abstract

The ultimate goal of cardiopulmonary resuscitation is to restore patient's brain function to its pre-arrest state. Fortunately, **the brain can tolerate global body ischaemia better than the heart** and post-arrest cardiac pump failure, which is a major determinant of the resuscitation course, can be remedied. That's why brain resuscitation is possible.

However, the quality of and the confidence in existing parameters to assess post-arrest neuroprognosis is low for many reasons - among others **the lack of standardized study approaches**. The American Heart Association report on standards for neuroprognostication in comatose survivors of cardiac arrest (AHAS) documents that to date **pupillometry is the only investigative standard** and **ACNS classification** of electrocortical activities and **Rankin-** or **Cerebral Performance Category Scale-** or **Health Related Quality of Life-**categorization of long-term neurological outcomes are **the only descriptive standards adopted in neuroprognostic research**.

AHAS suggest adhering to generally applicable principles for study design, execution, interpretation and reporting that are not developed specifically for post-arrest neuroprognostication. Brain stem reflexes, Glasgow Coma Scale scores, neurophysiological tests, biomarker-measurements and brain imaging are mentioned as prognostication tools. But, which test to choose or how and when to use it or how to interpret the findings is not specified.

The AHAS are endorsed by post-2000 data. The exclusion of evidence from earlier literature results in significant gaps. This report therefore **supplement AHAS by recapitulating previously published data on the neurology of cardiopulmonary arrest, on standardized bedside investigations and on interpretation of test results.**

The supremacy of bedside neuroprognosticators is emphasized. Clinical tests are in-expensive, generally accessible, applicable, easily taught and executed compared to biomarker measurements or brain imaging - and **relate directly to neurological outcomes:**

Serial testing of cranial nerve reflexes during basic life support **establish brain resuscitation capability** by the order and rate of reflex recoveries, neurological and EEG findings at ROSC **define unconsciousness** by it's components, serial neurological and EEG investigations during post-arrest unconsciousness **ascertain monitoring of the brain resuscitation course** by the order and concurrence of functions and **provide definite clues to predicting likely 'poor' or 'good' neurological perspectives within minutes to a few hours after start of cardiopulmonary resuscitation.**

Background

The American Heart Association (AHA) Emergency Cardiovascular Care Committee issued Standards for Studies of Neurological Prognostication in Comatose Survivors of Cardiac Arrest (AHAS) a year ago¹. Standards are needed to improve future studies because, as AHAS state:”the overall quality of existing neurological prognostication studies is low. As a consequence, the degree of confidence in the predictors and the subsequent outcomes is also low” *.

The AHAS aim at ” *examine the characteristics of neurological prognostication studies.... illustrate how biases affect these studies; provide quality standards and reporting requirements.... on the basis of existing standards for prognosis research; provide insights into the clinical elements currently used.... to improve their relevance to clinical practice; and provide suggestions to improve the scientific quality of neurological prognostication studies*” .

The document quotes but exceptionally reports on post-arrest neuroprognostication published before the year 2000. Of 211 quotations there are 3 reports on the impact of myoclonus and 2 on multimodal prognostication. The exclusion of evidence from earlier literature results in significant gaps.

Omitted are data on

salient features of the neurology after cardiopulmonary arrest with global ischemia (CA) from the start of basic life support (BLS) and throughout the first year after re-establishment of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) that are essential for the understanding of the character of neuroprognostication studies,

defined approaches to design and execution of neurological and EEG investigations and interpretation of test results in clinical practice that make comparison of research data possible, **parameters to predicting 'poor' or 'good' neuroprognosis within min during BLS and within the first few hours of post-resuscitation unconsciousness** that enable a shift from the currently recommended delayed and static approaches to early and dynamic neuroprognostication initiatives,

characteristics of neurological faculties and measures to establish patient's neurological peak performances after awakening that aim at avoiding 'surrogate' results ².

This report analyses AHAS paragraph by paragraph. Key statements are quoted and supplemented by recapitulating data from the existing literature on **bedside tests in adult victims of CA**. The techniques and results of biomarker- and brain imaging approaches are not commented upon.

*single quotation marks indicate inaccurate expressions, double marks precise quotations

Neurology of CA

AHAS state that:

"...the brain is injured directly as a result of loss of blood flow during arrest (no flow time) and the suboptimal flow that depends on the quality of CPR"

" brain injury is the primary and cardiovascular instability the second most common cause of in-hospital death after CA"

" Secondary neurological injury has also been described as a consequence of reperfusion after successful resuscitation "

"...(coma, stupor, vegetative state/unresponsive wakefulness syndrome, minimally conscious state, encephalopathy) are the most common neurological manifestations of hypoxic/ischemic brain injury"

Traditionally, the sum of global body ischemia prior to and during BLS is believed to harm the brain earlier and more severely than other bodily organs (e.g. the heart). A cascade of metabolic derangements is supposed to kill neurons within a few minutes of CA and to destroy the brain after 10 min. AHAS state accordingly that brain injury is the primary and cardiovascular instability the second most common cause of in-hospital death after CA. The statement is backed by retrospective data on mortality through 9 years in one ICU showing that 65 % of deaths resulted from neurological injury and 35 % from cardiogenic shock ¹.

However, experiments have evidenced that **animal brains can tolerate energy depletion and metabolic derangements due to complete ischemia for up to 20 min at 37 C** without any neurological sequelae if the post-arrest brain perfusion is adequate ; by contrast 5 min of selective and total arrest of the blood supply to the normal animal heart at normothermia invariably results in pump failure with inadequate perfusion of all vital organs ^{3,4}. Clinical experiences corroborate these findings: Of 111 patients with CA due to cardiovascular disease (the main source of CA) 93 (84 %) presented some brain function *during the efforts at resuscitation* ; twenty-four patients (24%) recovered some brain function (2 patients even consciousness) but could not have circulation restored (: they suffered "dissociated cardiac death") ; 18 (16%) were left in cardiogenic shock and had final asystole within 24 h. Half of 34 patients alive after 48 hours had heart pump failure ^{5,6}.

In another series of 231 patients heart failure was encountered in 176 (76 %). A total of 179 patients died. Clinical and postmortem findings suggested a primary cardiac disorder in 42%, extracardiac and extracerebral disorders (mainly pulmonary diseases) in 35% and brain death in 23% ⁷.

In conclusion, **the heart fails first in global body ischaemia and heart pump failure is a prominent feature and cause of death after CA.**

AHAS indicate that secondary brain deterioration may occur between 4 hours to 7 days after successful resuscitation *with awakening* due to early-after-CA brain reperfusion disorders. In our studies **no patient presented with delayed 'reperfusion injury'; deterioration related invariably to recurrent CA or haemodynamic- or ventilatory complications or metabolic derangements** ⁷.

The term coma covers a broad spectrum of brain dysfunctions from no function at all to the presence of cranial nerve reflexes (CNR), motor response to 'pain' (MRP), continuous cortical activity (CCA) in the EEG, eye opening and sleep-wake cycles (: 'open eye coma') in the absence of arousal and awareness ⁶. **Coma should be characterized by its distinctive neurological and EEG components and, distinguished from post-awakening features such as stupor and a minimally conscious state.**

The neurological and EEG findings at ROSC depict the sum of ischemic impacts upon the brain, define the coma status, give preliminary clues to the brain recovery capability and, serve as reference standards for further neurological assessments.

AHAS mention that differences in susceptibility to ischemia of various brain structures dictate the course of deterioration but do not detail the patterns of neurological recovery from CA.

Previous investigations clarified **the neurology of CA** as follows: *During postCA unconsciousness* spontaneous respiratory movements, pupillary light- coughing-swallowing- and ciliospinal reflexes appear in the mentioned order - and usually within the h after start of BLS ⁵. Then follows return of the caloric vestibular reflex and sequential appearances of joint neurological and EEG features - usually within 48 hrs: First, CNR + extensor-MRP (:decerebrate posturing) + no detectable cortical activity-EEG (NoDCA, strictly defined ⁶), then flexor- (: decorticate posturing) or stereotyped- (repetitive activity in CNR-innervated musculature) -MPR + bursts-suppressions-EEG (BS) and finally stereotyped- or defensive-MRP (: movements to localize or remove or avoid the stimulus) + continuous cortical activity-EEG (CCA). Myoclonies and epileptic phenomena occur transiently in patients with flexor- or stereotyped-MPR.

Patients pursue the same route of recovery irrespective of their eventual neurological outcome. But derailed brain resuscitation courses are identified by incomplete or stagnating recovery or losses of once recovered functions or by persistent myoclonus or epileptic phenomena ^{6,8}.

Awakening is signified by the presence of defensive-MRP, orienting eye movements and ability to obey simple orders. Defined motor, sensory and mental faculties return sequentially within days to months after awakening ⁶.

A similar description of the neurology of CA in patients treated by targeted temperature management with sedation and paralysis (TTM ect) does not exist. Prolonged recovery and invalidation of motor reflex- and -response tests should be expected. But, **pupillary reflex- and EEG investigations are not invalidated by TTMect and are useful to assess the brain resuscitation course during the setting.**

More studies of patients prior to, during and off TTMect have confirmed the trends of the neurology of CA outlined above, the sequential recovery of EEG features in particular ².

Neuroprognostication studies/ uni- or multivariable models

AHAS emphasize” ... *one of the most important messages to emerge from the literature is that the relationships between predictor variables and outcomes are not linear, nor are they likely to be restricted to a single approach for optimizing the prediction of outcome...*”,

index tests are ... indirectly measure of severity of brain injury after CA”.

Pre-2000 research of patients not treated by TTMect established that brain functions return during post-arrest unconsciousness in **a fixed order and exponentially interrelated in time**^{5,6,8}. Whether TTMect modifies these characteristics remains unknown.

The index test measures the function of its mediating structures directly - and their separation from other parts of the brain indirectly. The extensor-MRP, for example, is a spino-vestibular postural reflex and its presence indicates that spinal-, brain stem-, midbrain- and lower thalamus structures are functioning but released from forebrain control.

CA is, like brain trauma or stroke, commonly conceived to produce static brain injuries which determine the neurological fate. Most neuroprognosis studies therefore operate with 'poor' outcome (PO) -signs that resemble findings due to primary brain lesions. The currently recommended prognostication approaches were established in the pre-TTM era² and seem, like those, to herald that the more 'abnormal' a finding the 'poorer' the outcome.

No- or extensor-MRP, BS-EEG, myoclonics and epileptic phenomena have been acknowledged as PO- indicators but were considered inaccurate due to broad 95% confidence limits of low false positive rates⁹⁻¹¹. The inaccuracy of these prognosticators may be rooted in the fact that they can be natural features of brain revival towards an intact neurological survival. There is an **obvious risk of untimely withdrawal of life-sustaining support (WLST) if carers** who lack insight into the CA neurology **conceive features of natural brain recovery as signs of PO.**

Currently, no parameter is considered a stand-alone test. It is therefore strongly advised to deploy a combination of more clinical and/or paraclinical indices in 'multimodal' approaches to increase the confidence in outcome assessments⁹⁻¹¹.

AHAS mention **GOFAR** to exemplify a 'multimodal' approach. The system predicts survival to discharge with 'good' neurological outcome. Pre-existing critical illnesses in hospitalized patients are scored to identify individuals who would benefit from resuscitative attempts - *should a secondary CA occur*. It follows that the approach **does not apply directly to patients unconscious after resuscitation from primary CA**. Mentioned is also **the 2015 European Resuscitation Council (ERC) and European Society of Intensive Care Medicine (ESICM) suggested algorithm** to predict 'likely' PO: Absence of the pupillary light- and/ or corneal reflex and/ or lack of the N20 wave in traces of somatosensory evoked potentials (SSEP without a scalp recorded cortical response 20msec after electrical stimulation of a peripheral nerve) at 72 hours or later - when influences from TTMect supposedly have weaned - are emphasized as 'robust' predictors due to low false positive rates and narrow confidence limits. If the 'robust' criteria are not met it is

advised to await 24 hrs and then predict likely PO by establishing two or more clinical and/or paraclinical ominous signs (e.g. status myoclonus <48h from ROSC, unreactive BS or status epilepticus-EEG or high biomarker levels or signs of diffuse brain injuries on CT or MR-images) ¹⁰

#.The use of more adverse signs in combination is supposed to minimize the probability of false outcome assessments and untimely withdrawal of life-sustaining support.

The recommended multimodal approach would in any event **be expected to be inaccurate:** No- or extensor- or flexor-MRP, myoclonus and epileptic phenomena may emerge as intermediary features of a natural post-arrest brain revival as parts of a trajectory towards intact neurological survival as described above. The approach, moreover, **provides indirect evidence only because** it depends on single continuous variables endorsed by studies of low quality of evidence (qE) and on biomarker levels or brain images. The paraclinical tools have not been standardized, are rarely and selectively used and depict brain structural changes that do not relate consistently to clinical signs of brain dysfunction.

If CNR cannot be elicited it seems rational **at any time from ROSC** to perform the apnoea test in order to determine whether brain stem death has occurred. **Brain stem areflexia including irreversible apnoea is the only absolute predictor of PO** ⁸. Ancillary SSEP is not needed.

However, certain *preconditions must be met* before the apnoea test is performed:

Adequate evaluations up to and at the time of testing

have excluded confounding hemodynamic-, ventilatory-, metabolic derangements and medication and ascertained that brain functioning has deteriorated with losses of all CNR ⁶.

The october 2020 draft of ERC/ESICM guidelines presents a modified algorithm: It is suggested to estimate neuroprognosis in **patients with flexor- or poorer MRP** at or after more than 72 h. Now, is not advised to postpone prognostication if 'robust' criteria are not met it and areactive BS-EEG is no longer a recommended predictor.

The utility of the 2015 ERC/ESICM algorithm which focused on **patients with extensor or no MRP** has been tested. A retrospective study concluded that it seemed to perform better than other approaches ¹². However, evaluations of the performance of various versions of the algorithm disclosed that it failed to determine the outcome in a majority of patients and did not identify PO in many cases ^{13,14}.

The 2020 algorithm may perform even poorer than the 2015 version because patients with a flexor-MRP state are included !

Timing of outcome assessments and current measures

AHAS indicate that

"...COSCA suggestedoutcome after cardiac arrest is less influenced by locomotor problems",

"...the CPC and mRS have been extensively used..." but "... ILCOR suggested using mRS rather than the CPC... to measure functional recovery...",

"...AHA consensus... to assess neurological outcomes at 3 months after discharge",

and propose

"A combined assessment of both neurological outcome and HRQOL at 3 and 6 months at a minimum, plus at 1 year if resources permit".

Pre-2000 data demonstrated that motor, sensory and mental faculties return sequentially after awakening. Patient's performances changed significantly within days to months and **peaked at different time points**. Function capacities were measured by patient's ability to talk, stand and walk, to control bladder and gut, by their awareness of own data and of time, place and role of other persons and, by their ability to retain and recall ⁶. Evaluation of locomotor functions was important because **inability to stand and walk differentiated patients with transient or persistent severe disabilities from those with moderate or slight/no disabilities**.

The Rankin scale (RS) was developed to categorize outcomes after stroke ¹⁵ but modified (mRS) by adding the excellent health category to classify neurological performance after CA . The scale does not differentiate modes of death (: brain death, cardiac death or WLST) but ILCOR claimed that mRS differentiates moderate- from slight/no disabled patients better than the Cerebral Performance Category Scale (CPSC).

CPCS classifies the poorest outcome as brain death ¹⁶. A recent systematic review of bedside '**good' outcome studies** showed that **CPCS was exclusively used** ².

Both mRS and CPCS categorize outcomes by care dependency and social adaptability (which do not necessarily reflect neurological disorders) and, by ability to resume daily life activities (which do not exclude severe neurological deficits).

All function capacity schemes are limited by subjectiveness, irreproducibility and inadequacy to distinguish subgroups of disabled patients. Neurological sequelae are not differentiated clearly from impacts of other disabilities. Moreover, the schemes **do not capture what really matters to individuals in terms of acceptable and meaningful outcomes**. Some patients may be content with their life after CA although left with neurological deficits which to others seem

severely handicapping. Standardized health-related quality of life (HRQOL) instruments to supplement function capacity schemes should be promoted.

A previous study of patients not treated by TTMect showed that the observation times required to establish severe- or moderate- or no/slight disability at best were 6 months, 128 and 90 days from CA, respectively ⁶. It follows that **assessments at fixed, arbitrarily chosen, time points may establish 'surrogate' outcomes only.**

Quality of evidence and sources of bias in neuroprognostication studies

AHAS indicate that

" the overall quality of existing neurological prognostication studies is low."

" One of the most important biases...is self-fulfilling prophecy."

"..the treating team should be blinded to the results of the tests...."

"Another source of bias...is sedation and medications."

"...studies.... include patients who are not all comatose or... in coma for causes other than cardiac arrest..."

"..use of inconsistent thresholds of CPC and mRS for defining PO (and inconsistent)...reporting times for both neurological and HRQOL measures..."

The AHAS study-quality-statement concerns PO studies exclusively. But, **a recent systematic review of GO-prognostication studies showed that they were all of low quality of evidence (qE) ²**. The studies were qE downrated if they were observational or retrospective or small sample sized or not longitudinal, if coma was not defined or 'not truly unconscious' patients were included or lapses of time from CA or ROSC to index testing or outcome measurements were not recorded or long-term neurological outcome was established at random or at arbitrarily chosen times points (: risk of 'surrogate' outcome assessments) or lacked 'blinding'.

Eleven of the 21 studies reviewed were of low- or very-low quality of evidence (level 4 and 5) and 10 had more than five limitations to quality ². Thus, it is hereby established that **the overall quality of existing neurological prognostication studies is low.**

All the biases focused by AHAS obviously disqualify neuroprognostication studies. It is suggested that the probability of self-fulfilling prophecies can be reduced if comatose patients are maintained *" with full medical support until the time point of the measured outcome as specified in the study".*

This report suggests the **use of insight into the neurology of CA to diminish the risk of 'self-fulfilling' prophecies.**

However, **the overall low quality of existing neuroprognostication studies is mainly explained by intrinsic flaws in design and execution** as detailed above.

Length of clinical observation and prearrest -, intraarrest- and postarrest factors

AHAS state

”To rule out a delayed neurological recovery ..extend the observation period to 7 days after either the end of TTM or suspension of sedation...”

”...it is critical to ensure that the effects of confounding factors are eliminated, especially in the case of drug metabolism.”

Current guidelines recommend delaying prediction of PO at least 72 hours from ROSC in no-TTM patients, and 3-5 days or 72 hours after rewarming in TTMect patients⁹⁻¹¹. Most cases of death or of awakening are identified within these time spans; but awakening can be delayed 7 days or more and reperfusion injury may occur at any time from 4 hours to 7 days after ROSC- the AHAS state. However, **delayed 'reperfusion injuries' were not observed** in our studies; re-CA or hemodynamic-, or ventilatory- or metabolic derangements were invariably there⁶.

AHAS call for valid studies of the impact of pre-, intra- and post-arrest factors on neuroprognosis. Pre-2000 research has evidenced that **patients who initially presented with initial dysrhythmias other than ventricular fibrillation or had post-arrest heart failure or pulmonary complications less often than others regained the caloric vestibular reflex, CCA or consciousness and, that irreparable heart failure related significantly to brain death.** In our experience age, sex, medical history, cause and location of arrest and duration of BLS did not influence neurological recovery significantly⁶. It should be stressed that **non-neurological factors can portend indirect evidence only.**

The TTMect setting induces confounders. It is obviously important to account for patient's temperature, medication and hemodynamic- ventilatory- and metabolic states up to and at the time when neuroprognostication tests are performed.

Timing of neurological prognostication

AHAS emphasize

” Neurological prognostication of the post-cardiac arrest patient is a dynamic task, one that requires frequent evaluation and reevaluation to gauge recovery.”

AHAS do not endorse this statement by reference to the available literature at all. The current neuroprognostication guidelines suggest only a neurological examination at ROSC and a daily investigation thereafter ⁹⁻¹¹.

We have shown that

- i) **repeated brain stem reflex tests (optimally min per min) are required *during BLS*** - to discern favorable from unfavorable brain resuscitation courses ⁵,
- ii) **frequent (optimally hour per hour) checks of the order, linkages and rates of recovery of neurological signs and EEG patterns are needed from ROSC until consciousness returns or death occurs** - to monitor and predict the brain resuscitation course and identify definite neuroprognostic clues and,
- iii) **surveillance or serial checks (optimally week per week) of patient's performances are required *after awakening*** - to establish neurological outcomes at best ².

Registration of the time of testing is important because

no recovery of cranial nerve reflexes *at 30 min* from start of BLS forecasts persistent unconsciousness or severe post awakening disability,

brain stem areflexia *after more than one hour* predicts irreversible loss of any brain function ^{5,8},

failure of recovery of the ciliospinal- and/or caloric-vestibular reflex or of MRP *within the first 24 hours* from ROSC or losses of once recovered brain functions *at any time after ROSC* signify patients who would most likely stay unconscious until death ^{5,8}

and absent brain stem function with irreversible loss of spontaneous respiratory movements *at any time after ROSC* signifies that brain stem death is impending or has occurred ⁸.

Recovery of consciousness can be anticipated when pupillary light- and ciliospinal reflexes are present within less than 30 min after start of BLS ⁵ or the caloric vestibular reflex or stereotypic MRP encountered within 1 h from ROSC ⁸.

More studies of neuroprognostication by conventional- or automated EEG have established that a rate of CCA recovery of less than 24 h from ROSC relates to a 'good' neurological outcome ².

Bedside neurological examination

AHAS state

"Reporting level of consciousness can be subject to significant bias. One of the ways to minimize this is to use the GCS subscores ...to dichotomize the presence or absence of consciousness."

"A total...score <9 is traditionally used as the cutoff for coma..."

"... motor subscore of 6...indicates the patient's ability to follow commands."

The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) developers originally scored provoked or spontaneous motor-, verbal- and eye-responses in a worst to best order to classify the "depth of coma" in brain traumatology¹⁷. In resuscitation practice GCS scoring is mainly used to establish whether the patient is unconscious or awake. But, **GCS-evaluations may be invalidated by intubation, sedation and paralysis and by inadequate examination techniques e.g. when ill-defined stimulation techniques are used. Quantitative noxious, visual or auditory stimuli to ascertain and reproduce responses have been described**¹⁸.

In patients not treated by TTMect MRP corresponding to total GCS scores of 4-6 or motor scores of 1-3 are transient features of post-arrest unconsciousness whereas higher scores signify the awake patient⁶.

'Depth of coma' or 'level of consciousness' are irrational terms. **The heterogeneity of unconsciousness should be addressed by accounting for distinctive CNR, MRP and EEG components.**

AHAS list a series of brain stem reflexes but **do not mention the ciliospinal reflex!**

This reflex manifests by unilateral dilatation of the pupillary diameter following cutaneous 'noxious' stimulation - if present. The response is mediated by spinothalamic paths, lateral hypothalamus, midbrain, pons, brainstem and upper thoracic segments of the spinal medulla, the upper cervical ganglion and sympathetic nerves along the carotid artery plexus to the long ciliary nerve - which innervates the pupillo-dilatator muscle. **The ciliospinal reflex is more easily assessed than the light response early after CA when miosis (pupillary diameter < 2mm) is a prominent feature**⁵. **The ciliospinal reflex test is of crucial importance for the assessment of brain stem function state early after CA and carries a particularly high neuroprognostic weight**^{5,8}.

AHAS do not describe standard approaches to perform, interpret and document the results of brain stem function testing. It is important to specify **the tests chosen, the technical standard used and when, how and how often to deploy the test and how to interpret and document the test results**. A study protocol should detail the investigative techniques and guide to interpretation and documentation of results.

The battery of tests should include

the apnoe test,

the pupillary response to light stimuli of defined intensity and duration,

the pupillary response to cutaneous 'noxious' stimuli (:electrical shocks) of defined intensity and duration (the ciliospinal reflex),

the motor response to cutaneous electrical stimuli of defined intensity and duration

(to identify i) no response, ii) decerebrate posturing (: extension-pronation of all four limbs and extension of the neck), iii) decorticate posturing (: flexion of upper limbs and extension of lower limbs), iv) stereotyped movements (:repetitive activities of cranial nerve innervated musculature e.g. grimacing, eyeballing, chewing, swallowing) or v) defensive responses (:movements to localize, remove or avoid the stimulus))

and eye movements in response to irrigation of the outer ear meatus with ice water (the caloric vestibular reflex)^{5,6,18}.

Test results should be documented. The apnoe test requires checks of arterial pO₂ and pCO₂ and recording of possible chest movements or of tracheal air flow. The test should be performed only when CNR cannot be elicited and specified preconditions are met- to establish brain stem death¹⁸. Pupillary size changes can be documented by pupillometry or by video-recording, motor responses to 'pain' documented by video-recording and, the caloric vestibular reflex by tracing eye movements from frontal electrodes or by video-recording.

There are no standards for testing the corneal-, gag- and 'doll-eye' reflexes.

It seems reasonable to prefer testing of the pupillary light- and ciliospinal reflexes during BLS and, to deploy pupillary-and (when feasible) caloric vestibular-reflex- and MRP-examinations after ROSC.

It is obviously important to note down the time-lapse from CA or ROSC to the time of testing.

Ancillary EEG and SSEP

AHAS state:

"Ancillary testing augments the clinical examination but does not replace its importance..."

"...larger numbers (of EEG electrodes) providing greater anatomic information and improved ability to discriminate signal from artifact."

"...standardization of reactivity testing is currently lacking..."

"To date, lack of reactivity has correlated with poor outcome. "

"... patterns that may correlate with poor outcome.... include malignant features such as burst-suppression pattern, low voltage, SE, and stimulus-induced...ictal discharges and identical bursts"

CNR and MRP examinations may be sufficient to assess the brain resuscitation course in patients not treated by TTMect - or before that treatment is installed. **But, during TTMect and rewarming, when more CNR and any MRP may be concealed, EG becomes an essential tool for neuro-monitoring and -prediction.**

AHAS do not discuss EEG examination approaches, electrode montages or the number of EEG leads. Pre-2000 research showed that the **post-CA EEG patterns usually are global** (:not focal)⁶. **A simple approach using a pair of leads would be adequate to trace the main EEG configurations** that are encountered during post-arrest unconsciousness: **No-detectable cortical activity, bursts-suppressions, continuous cortical activity and 'epileptic' phenomena** (: predominant spike/sharpwave discharges).

Identification of 'artifacts' – if not recognized right away- may require particularly demanding measures to reduce or eliminate extracerebral signals that interfere with cortical activities ¹⁷.

EEG 'reactivity' (: any change of configurations following stimulation) is claimed to predict PO if absent and GO if present. 'Reactivity' has been assessed following nipple pinching or pinprick or fingernail- or supraorbital notch pressure or 'noise' ². **Quantitative visual, auditory and noxious stimulation techniques** to ascertain and reproduce responses are available ^{18,19} but have so far **rarely been used in neuroprognostication studies**. Electrostimulation is used to control neuromuscular blockade in anaesthesiological practice and would qualify investigations of the ciliospinal reflex, MRP and EEG 'reactivity'.

EEG classification according to the ANCS nomenclature ²⁰ is not specific to description of post-CA EEG; it defines configurations caused by various critical illnesses. Identification of the post-CA main EEG patterns mentioned above will do for monitoring and predicting the brain resuscitation course in practice,

Negatively loaded terms are unfortunate. **The so-called 'malignant' features e.g. low voltage-, BS- patterns and ictal discharges may be encountered during the natural brain revival course towards intact neurological survival ⁶ and, when misconceived, lead to untimely WLST !**

EEG should be promoted as it seems seldomly used. Analyses of 208.000 records on hospitalized cases of CA in the USA from 2006-12 revealed that nationwide less than 2 % had EEG performed ²¹. More recent data seem not available.

Somatosensory evoked potentials (SSEP) are not invalidated by TTMect. The examination is useful throughout post resuscitation unconsciousness to detect disorders of the periphero-cortical pathways; it establishes cortical responsiveness and seems so far **a useful indicator of PO when absent for hours ^{2,9-11}**. SSEP investigations are expertise demanding and rarely accessible in resuscitation practice.

Standards for design, execution, interpretation and reporting studies

"...studies should adhere to ..standards..."

Adherence to quality principles for study design, execution, interpretation and reporting of results e.g. the GRADE- STARD-, TRIPOD-, PRISMA- and CONSORT approaches would undoubtedly improve future studies to some extent. But **standards should be pertinent to studies of neuroprognosis after CA** and focus on

large or calculated size patient cohorts, modelled reference standards, primary CA, aetiology of CA, location of arrest, initial cardiac dysrhythmia,

standard index tests, defined examination techniques including use of quantitative stimulation, repeated CNR tests during BLS, neurological and EEG status at ROSC,

frequent CNR+MRP +EEG testing during post-arrest unconsciousness (during TTMect serial pupillary reflex tests + EEG),
apnoea test (when preconditions are met),
surveillance of patient's neurological performances after awakening (through months, if necessary),
by longitudinal standard neurological function-capacity and HRQOL tests,
precise indications of the time-lapses from CA or ROSC to index testing and to measurements of long-term neurological outcome and
recording of possible confounders present up to and at the time of index testings and outcome measurements.

Key messages

Pre-2000 studies evidenced that
brain resuscitation after CA is possible because the brain may tolerate global body ischemia better than the heart and because post-arrest heart pump failure can be remedied.

Heart pump failure is a major determinant of the post-resuscitation course.

Recurrent CA or other hemodynamic- or ventilatory complications or metabolic derangements explain why brain functions deteriorate after awakening - rather than a 'delayed reperfusion injury'.

Unconsciousness should be characterized by its distinctive neurological and EEG components and distinguished from post-awakening features such as stupor and a minimally conscious state.

Standardizable neurological tests are the apnoea test, pupillary response to light and 'pain', motor activity in response to 'pain' and eye movements in response to irrigation of the outer ear meatus with ice water.

A pair of leads seem adequate to trace the main EEG configurations during post-arrest unconsciousness (: no-detectable cortical activity-, bursts-suppressions-, continuous cortical activity-EEG and 'epileptic' discharges).

Brain stem functions appear in fixed and interdependent order – respiratory movements and more cranial nerve reflexes usually within the hour after start of BLS; then follows return of the caloric vestibular reflex and sequential appearances of concurrent neurological and EEG features - usually within 48 hrs. Patients pursue the same route of recovery during unconsciousness irrespective of their eventual neurological outcome; but, derailed brain resuscitation is identified by incomplete or stagnating recovery or losses of once recovered functions or by seizure phenomena.

Repeated brain stem reflex tests are required during BLS and frequent checks of the order, linkages and rates of recovery of neurological signs and EEG from ROSC until consciousness returns or death occurs are needed to gauge brain recovery or deterioration.

Surveillance of patient's performances are required after awakening to establish neurological outcome at best.

No recovery of cranial nerve reflexes *at 30 min* from start of BLS forecast persistent unconsciousness or severe post awakening disability, brain stem areflexia after more than *one hour* predict irreversible loss of any brain function, failure of recovery of the ciliospinal- and/or caloric-vestibular reflex or of MRP *within the first 24 hours* from ROSC, or losses of once recovered brain functions *at any time after ROSC* signify patients who would most likely stay unconscious until death and, absent brain stem function including irreversible loss of spontaneous respiratory movements *at any time after ROSC* signifies brain stem death.

Recovery of consciousness can be anticipated when pupillary light- and ciliospinal reflexes are present within less than 30 min after start of BLS or when the caloric vestibular reflex or stereotypic MRP are encountered within 1 h from ROSC.

Awakening is signified by the presence of defensive-MRP, orienting eye movements and ability to obey simple orders. Defined motor, sensory and mental faculties return sequentially and patient's performances peak within days to months after awakening. Inability to stand and walk differentiated patients with transient or persistent severe disabilities from those with moderate or slight/no disabilities.

Standardizable index tests are the apnoea test, pupillary light- and 'pain'- reflexes, motor response to 'pain' and the caloric vestibular reflex.

The ciliospinal reflex test is of crucial importance for the assessment of brain stem function and carries a particularly high neuroprognostic weight.

Quantitative visual, auditory and noxious stimulation techniques are available and should be used to ascertain and reproduce responses in neuroprognostication research.

Patients with initial dysrhythmias other than ventricular fibrillation, post-arrest heart failure or pulmonary complications less often than others regained the caloric vestibular reflex, CCA or consciousness. Irremediable heart failure relates significantly to brain death.

The neurological and EEG findings at ROSC depict the sum of ischemic impacts upon the brain, define the state of unconsciousness, give preliminary clues to the brain recovery capability and serve as reference standard for further neurological assessments.

Prolonged recovery and invalidation of motor reflex- and -response tests should be expected due to hypothermia, sedation and paralysis. But, pupillary reflex- and EEG investigations are not invalidated by TTMect and should be used to assess the brain resuscitation course during the setting.

The index test measures the function of its mediating structures directly.

Registration of time lapse reckoned from CA or ROSC to the time of index testing or outcome measurement is important.

Standards for design, execution, interpretation and reporting studies should be pertinent to studies of neuroprognosis after CA.

The multimodal approach recommended by resuscitation guidelines to predict likely PO provide indirect evidence only and may fail in a majority of patients.

Conclusions

The ultimate goal of cardiopulmonary resuscitation is to restore patient's brain function to its pre-arrest state. That's possible because **the brain can tolerate global body ischemia better than the heart** and because heart pump failure, the major determinant of the resuscitation course, can be remedied. However, only some 10 % of the patients left unconscious after resuscitation achieve a 'good' neurological outcome presumably because guidelines to predicting 'good' neurological outcome do not exist and WLST is practiced when patients present signs that are conceived to indicate adversity. The quality of and the confidence in existing neuroprognostication studies is low for various reasons - among others due to **lack of standards for design and execution**. AHAS document that **pupillometry is the only investigative standard** and **ACNS classification** of EEG, **Rankin-** or **Cerebral Performance Category Scale-** or **Health Related Quality of Life-** categorization of long-term neurological outcomes **the only descriptive standards adopted in neuroprognostic research**. AHAS is primarily a catalogue of possible initiatives to improve future studies. It is suggested to adhere to principles for study design, execution, interpretation and reporting that are not pertinent to studies of neuroprognosis after CA.

Moreover, **AHAS suffer from gaps because informations from the pre-2000 literature have been omitted**. This report therefore recapitulates previously published data that characterized clinical neuroprognostication studies, standardized bedside investigations, specified factors which are important for rating study quality of evidence, described approaches to assess the CA impact on the brain and to monitor and predict brain resuscitation courses and outcomes during post-arrest unconsciousness. Moreover, means to determine patient's neurological outcome at best after awakening are addressed.

" The goal is to have accurate, precise, and clinically applicable test for most patients after cardiac arrest that can be applied as early as possible after resuscitation" – the AHAS state. The Pre-2000 research did in fact demonstrate how **bedside tests can provide definite clues to predicting 'poor' as well as 'good' neurological outcomes within min to a few hours after cardiopulmonary arrest in unconscious adults**.

This document emphasizes the supremacy of bedside assessments of neuroprognosis in resuscitation practice. The clinical findings relate directly to neurological outcomes and CNR, MRP and EEG-tests are, unlike paraclinical examinations, generally accessible, suitable, applicable and inexpensive, easily taught, executed and documented.

Abbreviations

AHAS, American Heart Association Standards

CA, cardiopulmonary arrest with global body ischaemia

CPR, cardiopulmonary resuscitation

BLS, basic life support

ROSC, re-establishment of spontaneous circulation

CNR, cranial nerve reflex

MRP, motor response to 'pain'

EEG, electroencephalogram

NoDCA, no detectable cortical aticity

BS, bursts-suppressions

CCA, continuous cortical activity

TTMect, targeted temperature management with sedation and paralysis

PO, 'poor' outcome

GO, 'good' outcome

WLST, withdrawal of life-sustaining support

GOFAR, Good Outcome Following Attempted Resuscitation

ERC/ESICM, European Resuscitation Council/European Society of Intensive Care Medicine

CT, computer tomography

MR, magnet resonance

qE, quality of evidence

CPCS, cerebral performance category scale

mRS, modified Rankin scale

COSCA, Core Outcome Set for Cardiac Arrest

ILCOR, International Liason Committee on Resuscitation

GCS, Glasgow Coma Scale

ACNS, American Clinical Neurophysiological Society

SSEP, somatosensory evoked potential

GRADE, Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Developement and Evaluation

STARD, Standards for Reporting Systematic Accuracy Studies

TRIPOD, Transparent Reporting of a Multivarible Predicting model for Individual Prognosis and Diagnosis

PRISMA, Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Metaanalyses

CONSORT, Consolidated Standamnrd for Reporting Trials

References

1. Geocardin GR, Callaway CW, Fink EL, Golan E, Greer DM, Ko NU, Lang E, Licht DJ, Marino BS, McNair ND, Peberdy MA, Perman SM, Sims DB, Soar J, Sandroni Cc. Standards for studies of neurological prognostication in comatose survivors of cardiac arrest: A scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Circulation* 2019;140:e517-e542.
2. Jørgensen EO, Holm S. Clinical approaches to assess neurological outcome of cardiopulmonary arrest in unconscious adults. [Http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4084887](http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4084887). Previously versions denied publication in *Resuscitation* 2017 (D-18-00306), *Intensive Care Med* 2018 (D-18-00867), *Acta Neurol Scand* and *Brain & behaviour* 2019 (R-03-19-109), *Acta Anaesth Scand* (20-0587) and *Circulation* 2020 (2020/051594).
3. Hirsch H, Euler KH, Schneider M. U'ber die erholung und wiederbelebung des gehirns nach ischa'mie bei normothermia. *Pfl'ugers Arch* 1975;265:281-313.
4. Miller JR, Myers RE, Neurologic effects of systemic circulatory arrest in the monkey, *Neurology* 1970;20: 715-725.
5. Jørgensen EO. Course of neurological recovery and cerebral prognostic signs during cardiopulmonary resuscitation. *Resuscitation* 1997;35:9-16.
6. Jørgensen EO and Holm S. The natural course of neurological recovery following cardiopulmonary resuscitation. *Resuscitation* 1998;36:11-22.
7. Jørgensen EO and Holm S. The course of circulatory and cerebral recovery after circulatory arrest: influence of pre-arrest, arrest and post-arrest factors. *Resuscitation* 1999;42:173-182.
8. Jørgensen EO, Holm S. Prediction of neurological outcome after cardiopulmonary resuscitation. *Resuscitation* 1999;41:145-152.
9. Callaway CW, Soar J, Aibiki M, Bottger BW, Brooks SC, Deakin CD, Donnino MW, Drajer S, Kloeck W, Morley PT, Morrison LJ, Neumar R, Nicholson TC, Molan JP, Okada K, O'Neil BJ, Paiva EF, Parr MJ, Wang T-L, Witt J. Part 4. Advanced life support. International Consensus on Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation and Emergency Cardiovascular Care Science with treatment recommendations. *Circulation* 2015;132 issue 16 suppl 1: 84-145.
10. Nolan JP, Soar J, Cariou A, Cronberg T, Mouleart VRM, Deakin CD, Bottger BW, Friberg H, Sunde K, Sandroni C. European Resuscitation Council and European Society of Intensive Care Medicine Guidelines for Postresuscitation Care 2015: Section 5 of the European Resuscitation Council Guidelines for resuscitation 2015. *Resuscitation* 2015; 95:201-222.
11. Callaway CW, Donnino MW, Fink EL, Geocardin RG, Golan E, Kern KB, Leary M, Meurer W, Peberdy MA, Thomson TM, Zimmerman JL. American Heart Association Guidelines Update for Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation and Emergency Cardiovascular Care. Part 8: Post-Cardiac Arrest Care. *Circulation* 2015;132 (suppl 132):S465-S482.

12. Zhou SE, Marciel CB, Ormseth CH, Beekman R, Gilmore EJ, Greer DM, Distinct predictive values of current neuroprognostic guidelines in post-cardiac arrest patients. *Resuscitation* 2019;139:343-50.
13. Bongiovanni F, Romagnosi F, Barbella G, Di Rocco A, Rosetti AO, Taccone FS, Sandroni Cc, Oddo M. Standardized EEG analysis to reduce the uncertainty of outcome prognostication after cardiac arrest. *Intensive Care Med* 2020 DOI:10.1007/s00134-019-05921-6.
14. Moseby-Knappe M, Westhall E, Backman S, Mattson-Carlgren N, Draganecea I, Lybeck A, Friberg H, Stammet P, Lilja G, Horn J, Kjærgaard J, Rylander C, Hassager C, Ullen S, Nielsen N, Cronberg T. Performance of a guideline-recommended algorithm for prognostication of poor neurological outcome after cardiac arrest. *Intensive Care Med* 2020. Oct ;46(10): 1852-62.
15. Rankin L. Cerebral vascular accidents in patients over the age of 60. II. Prognosis. *ScottMed J* 1957;2 (5):200-215.
16. Safar P. Resuscitation after brain ischaemia. In: Grenvik A and Safar P (eds) *Brain failure and resuscitation*. Churchill Livingstone New York 1981:155-847.
17. Teasdale G and Jennett B. Assessment of coma and impaired consciousness. A practical scale. *Lancet*, 1974;2:81-84.
18. Jørgensen EO. Clinical note. EEG without detectable cortical activity and cranial nerve areflexia as parameters of brain death. *Electroencephalogr Clin Neurophysiol* 1974;36:70-75.
19. Jørgensen EO. Technical contribution. Requirements for recording the EEG at high sensitivity in suspected brain death. *Electroencephalogr Clin Neurophysiol* 36: 65- 69.
20. Hirsch LJ, LaRoche SM, Gaspard N, Gerard E, Svoronos A, Herman ST, Mani R, Ariff H, Jette N, Minard Y, Kerrigan JF, Vespa P, Hantus S, Claassen J, Young GB, So E, Kaplan PW, Nuwer MR, Fountain NB, Drislane FW. American Clinical Neurophysiology Society's Standardised critical care EEG terminology 2012 version. *J Clin Neurophysiol* 2013;30:1-27.
21. Rush B, Ashkanani M, Romano K, Hertz P. Utilization of electroencephalogram post-cardiac arrest in the United States: A nationwide retrospective cohort analysis. *Resuscitation* 2017;110:141-145.